

**CERTAINES CONSIDÉRATIONS SUR LES PARTICULARITÉS
PSYCHOLINGUISTIQUES DE LA TRADUCTION ET DE L'AUTOTRADUC-
TION COMME PROCESSUS DE MÉDIATION CULTURELLE /
SOME CONSIDERATIONS ON THE PSYCHOLINGUISTIC PECULIARITIES
OF TRANSLATION AND SELF-TRANSLATION AS A PROCESS
OF CULTURAL MEDIATION**

Daniela PREASCA, PhD Student

(^oAlecu Russo Balti State University, Republic of Moldova)

preascadaniela@gmail.com

<https://orcid.org/0009-0004-1826-2727>

Received: June 1, 2025 | Reviewed: June 3, 2025 | Accepted: June 5, 2025

UDC 81 | DOI from Zenodo

In this research we try to examine the psycholinguistic peculiarities of translation and self-translation as a process of cultural mediation in multilingual spaces. It adopts a multidisciplinary approach (primarily psycholinguistic, but also experimental, comparative, and analytical at the discourse level), focusing on the Republic of Moldova, where several languages coexist, including Romanian, Russian, Gagauz, and Ukrainian, among others. The data from the Republic of Moldova are compared with those recorded in other multilingual societies (such as Canada, Belgium, Switzerland, and Catalonia). Validated data (censuses, empirical studies) are used to support the analysis. The investigation is theoretically grounded in the works of Grosjean, Jeanneret, Pavlenko, Kroll, Bialystok, and others. Two tables that summarize the demolinguistic data and the comparative and cognitive performances support the research. This leads

to the proposal of a model that schematizes linguistic distribution in the Republic of Moldova, alongside another that illustrates in detail the cerebral mechanisms of bilingualism in general, and Bessarabian bilingualism in particular. Concrete cases (bilingual writers, educational policies) are also mentioned and presented to argue the theoretical approach. The analysis demonstrates that translation and self-translation involve cognitive mechanisms of inhibition and control specific to bilinguals, shaping complex identity dynamics. These linguistic processes are strongly influenced by the sociocultural context, including language status, linguistic policies, and inter-ethnic contacts. In conclusion, we emphasize the importance of considering psycholinguistic dimensions in language education, cultural mediation, the understanding of identity dynamics in bilingual communities, and the processes of translation and self-translation.